

PLASTIC SHRINKAGE CRACKING BEHAVIOUR OF ALKALI ACTIVATED 3D PRINTABLE MIXTURES

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ABSTRACT

Plastic shrinkage cracking is a critical issue in concrete construction, affecting the durability and structural integrity of concrete elements. The present study investigates the plastic shrinkage cracking behavior of alkali-activated 3D concrete printable mixtures, considering the effect of restrained conditions. The research employs a comprehensive experimental approach, encompassing fresh properties, strength (workability and compressive strength), and plastic shrinkage cracking assessment tests. Various alkali-activated mixes were formulated using different combinations of fly ash and slag as binders, with sodium hydroxide (NaOH) serving as the activator at a concentration of 14 M. Each mixture was prepared consistently, maintaining a constant water-to-binder ratio of 0.35. These tests are conducted under controlled environmental conditions to evaluate crack formation and crack width. Additionally, crack analysis was performed using numerical computing techniques to provide detailed insights into crack characteristics. To determine the workability for a printable mixture, a flow table test was conducted, selecting the mixture with an initial slump flow of 176 mm and a slump of 45 mm. This mixture remained within the printable range after remixing, which redistributed moisture and reduced viscosity, enabling additional workability. The selected mixture achieved a compressive strength of 58.70 MPa at 28 days and exhibited delayed cracking compared to OPC mortar. Crack analysis using MATLAB provided detailed measurements of crack dimensions.

Keywords: *3DCP, Alkali activation, Plastic Shrinkage cracking, Durability*

after 30 minutes, the mixture fell out of the printable range. However, upon remixing, the mixture regained a printable slump range for an additional 40 minutes. Remixing reintroduced shear forces, redistributing the moisture and breaking up the early formation of the stable aluminosilicate gel. This restored the mix to a printable state by temporarily reducing the viscosity and reactivating the workability. Also, compressive strength tests were performed on the selected mix at 3, 7, and 28 days as shown in Fig.3(b). The alkali-activated mix achieved a strength of 58.70 MPa which is attributed to the stable, low-permeability gel that forms during the chemical reactions.

Figure 3: (a) Slump characteristics of AAM mixture (b) Compressive strength of AAM mixture.

In addition, the cracking behavior of alkali-activated mortar was investigated using two different mould shapes under restraint effect. When compared to OPC mortar, the cracks in the alkali system emerged after the completion of a 10 h plastic shrinkage crack test in both mould types. This delayed cracking phenomenon was observed, indicating a notable shrinkage difference compared to OPC mortar as shown in Fig.4(a,b).

As stated in previous literature ((Mataalkah et al (2019); Yang et al (2022); Ye & Radlińska (2017)), alkali-activated mortar exhibits less plastic shrinkage strain and delayed cracking compared to ordinary Portland cement (OPC) concrete due to several factors. AAM has a lower bleeding tendency, which minimizes surface water loss and shrinkage. It also has higher viscosity and yield stress, providing greater resistance to deformation. The chemical reactions in AAM create a stable, low-permeability aluminosilicate gel that retains moisture better. These factors, along with favourable rheological properties, reduce early-age deformations and delay cracking in alkali activated mortar.

Figure 4: Comparative Analysis of cracking behaviour of AAM and OPC mortar under (a) normal (b) mould shape restraint condition.

The crack analysis of alkali-activated mortar was conducted using MATLAB. This MATLAB script, written to analyse crack width, crack length, and crack area, detects and measures cracks in an image

through various image processing techniques. The process begins by reading and converting the image to grayscale, followed by enhancing the image and creating a binary representation to highlight the cracks. Noise reduction is achieved using median filtering, and morphological operations are employed to refine the edges. Precise crack boundaries are identified through Canny edge detection. Subsequently, the script identifies the largest crack, traces its boundary, and calculates its length, width, and area. To ensure accurate measurements, a reference image with a known scale is utilized to convert pixel measurements to millimeters. The dimensions of the crack are then displayed as shown in fig.5, providing detailed information essential for crack assessment. When compared to an OPC mix, which exhibited a crack area of 1.81 mm², a width of 0.21 mm, and a length of 38.1 mm, the alkali-activated mix demonstrated significantly smaller crack dimensions, with a length of 15.50 mm, a width of 0.18 mm, and an area of 0.62 mm². This comparison indicates that the alkali-activated mix experiences considerably less plastic shrinkage cracking than OPC. The reduced crack dimensions in the alkali-activated mix suggest better performance in mitigating early-age deformations and lower susceptibility to plastic shrinkage compared to the traditional OPC mortar.

Figure 5: Crack analysis using MATLAB

3. Conclusions

The study on alkali-activated 3D printable mixtures revealed significant findings regarding their plastic shrinkage cracking behavior. Monitoring slump loss showed that remixing restored printability by reintroducing shear forces, redistributing moisture, and disrupting the early formation of stable aluminosilicate gel. Compressive strength tests demonstrated the mix's strength attributed to the low-permeability gel formed during chemical reactions. Compared to OPC mortar, alkali-activated mortar exhibited less plastic shrinkage and delayed cracking due to factors like lower bleeding tendency, higher viscosity, and the formation of a stable gel. Crack analysis using MATLAB provided precise measurements essential for assessing cracks. Overall, these results highlight the benefits of alkali-activated mixtures in mitigating early-age deformations and delaying cracking compared to traditional OPC mortar.

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